

THE HUMAN MEMOME PROJECT

Text-data analytics to find socio-cultural predictors of longevity utilising the Quantified Self, crowdsourcing and citizen science communities

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Background

- We aim to use text data-analytics to find prognostic, diagnostic and real-time markers for health, longevity and risks to longevity.
- The toolsets of computational linguistics, text-data analysis and machine learning have proved valuable in forensics, marketing, psychological analysis and investment as well as responding to terrorism¹ and crises². We build upon these previous uses by surveying and correlating factors previously associated with longevity³⁻⁸, with words and word sets.
- Searching for classes of longevity marker that are low resolution, but non-invasive, easily sampled and are potentially available in real-time via the internet and social media was the driver behind the first citizen science and crowdsourcing experiment from **The Human Memome Project (HMP)**.
- Hard Aims:** Find words, phrases, text-health correlations and word-biometric combinatorial markers that associate with longevity, and use these to develop new methods.
- Soft Aims:** Engage academia, citizen science, and the Quantified Self communities about the potential of text data and longevity as a subject of interest and health. Start a community and participant network. Create an open science commons dataset.

Data Collection

- Data was collected online through the HMP website through crowdsourcing platforms, and the Quantified Self and citizen scientist communities. Data recorded included biometrics previously correlated to longevity³⁻⁸, attitudes towards long life, and answers to questions about social, personality and behavioural patterns.

Word usage correlated to grip strength longevity predictor

Meme	r	p-value
helping	0.99	<0.01
correct	0.99	<0.01
lifestyle	0.97	0.01
peoples	0.97	0.01
kitchen	0.97	0.01
loving	0.97	0.01
proud	0.96	0.01
girlfriend	0.96	0.01
environment	0.96	0.01
surrounding	0.95	0.01
relationship	0.95	0.01
park	0.95	0.01
normally	0.95	0.01
hurt	0.95	0.01
teaching	0.94	0.02
taught	0.94	0.02
taken	0.94	0.02
shivaya	0.94	0.02
raise	0.94	0.02
opened	0.94	0.02
issues	0.94	0.02
happily	0.94	0.02
growing	0.94	0.02
finally	0.94	0.02
entire	0.94	0.02
encouraged	0.94	0.02
desire	0.94	0.02
decrease	0.94	0.02
culture	0.94	0.02
cats	0.94	0.02
particular	-0.94	0.02

Table 1. Top positive and negative correlations with grip strength longevity predictor³

Figure 1. Correlations between words with grip strength longevity predictor³ Words significantly correlated with grip strength are highlighted in red.

- The distribution of correlation between words and grip strength show that individual words can be associated with, and ranked by, a longevity predictor (Fig 1)
- Words that correlate with grip strength include behaviours, relationships, people lifestyles, concepts and environments (Table 1)
- Only 1 word was identified as significantly negatively correlated with grip strength

Geographic heat maps for self-reported health and attitudes related to living as long as possible

Figure 2. Self-reported Health. Identified as longevity predictor⁶

Figure 3. Answers to "Do you want to live as long as possible?"

Figure 4. Answers to "Do you want to continue living no matter what?"

- Globally participants (of varied health) showed an interest in want to live a long time regardless of health (Fig.2-3), but show global variability and strong local variability in surety in answering whether they want to live a long time no matter what kind of life that is (Fig 4).
- This information is important for future surveys and polls addressing health, longevity predictors, attitudes to longevity and attitudes as longevity predictors.

Open Science Dataset

- To develop interest and spur innovation in text-biometric data analytics for longevity we created an open science dataset available to academia and other interested parties – creating an online 'memome' database.
- We asked participants whether they consented to have their anonymised data be part of an open science dataset and a large majority opted in.
- The dataset is available here:** <http://www.thehumanmemomeproject.com/#/data/ck65>

Outcomes

- Proof-of-principle correlations between words and longevity predictor and mapped attitudes towards long life versus participant self-reported health.
- Presented at The Quantified Self London Meetup Group and The Quantified Self Conference EU 2013.
- Created an online open science dataset and started to build a citizen science community.
- Future - analysis of social media text and health app data, analysis of survival data, validation versus biomarkers and development of real-time analytics

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